

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-SYSTEM THINKING BASED ON MOTIVATION, ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT, AND ACADEMIC DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED BY PUPILS IN SCIENCE 4

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to describe the relationship between Grade 4 pupils' self-system thinking based on motivation encompassing intrinsic, career, self-determination, self-efficacy; their academic achievement in terms of written works, performance tasks, and quarterly examinations; and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4. The study utilized descriptive-correlational research design involving 201 Grade 4 pupils in a public elementary school. The data was gathered using the Science Motivation Questionnaire II (SMQ-II), and a researchers-made questionnaire. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, median, interquartile range, and Spearman's rho were used to analyze the data. Results reveal that pupils' self-system thinking based on motivation in learning Science 4 are intrinsically and career-motivated, self-determined, have sense of self-efficacy, and motivated by their grades in Science. The Grade 4 pupils did not encounter difficulties in learning Science with their academic achievement of fairly satisfactory to very satisfactory. The self-efficacy as motivational factor is significantly correlated with academic difficulties in Science 4 and academic achievement in terms of performance tasks; while there is a weak negative correlation between academic achievement and academic difficulties in Science 4 in terms of written works. This study highlights the importance of self-efficacy, believing in one's ability to learn, for both overcoming difficulties and achieving success in Science 4. Efforts to boost students' self-efficacy in Science can lead to better understanding and achievement in performance tasks. Furthermore, improving written work performance may require a shift

in teaching methods to focus on deeper conceptual understanding and connections between science ideas.

Keywords: *self-system thinking based on motivation, academic achievement, academic difficulties*

INTRODUCTION

Science education is a cornerstone of academic development, providing students with essential skills and knowledge for understanding the natural world and fostering critical thinking abilities. In the Philippine educational journey, Grade 4 marks a pivotal stage in the domain of Science when pupils begin to delve into more complex scientific concepts. The transition from Grade 3 to level 4 can be accompanied by a range of academic difficulties. These difficulties can manifest as challenges in understanding concepts, low grades, reduced engagement, and decreased motivation. It is during this phase that motivation in the sense of self-system thinking plays a fundamental role in shaping pupils' academic experiences (Maryani et al., 2023). Understanding the relationship between pupils' self-system and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science is essential for educators and policymakers to create effective learning environments that cater to the unique needs of Grade 4 pupils (Magulod, 2019).

For several years, learners' poor achievement level in Science has been documented. In the news reported by Baclig (2020) with the headline, "PH's Grade 4 students lowest in Math, Science around the world — int'l study", uncovered that the Philippines scored 249 in Science which is significantly lower compared to other participating countries. The country ranked lowest among 58 countries in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2019 (TIMSS). The interpretation of the results of the Filipino pupils' performance on the assessment on the TIMSS fourth grade Science achievement scale indicated as Low International Benchmark which shows that they have limited understanding of scientific concepts and limited knowledge of foundational Science facts (Mullis et al., 2020). A decrease of 83 points from 332 in 2013 to 249 in 2019 shows a clear deterioration in Science achievement.

Even the results in Programme for International Student Assessment's (PISA) 2022, an international assessment that measures 15-year-old learners' reading, mathematics, and Science literacy showed that the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally. The country scored approximately 120 points lower than the average scores, with scores of 355 in math, 347 in reading. In Science, the country's average performance was 356 points compared to the last PISA 2018 results which was 357 points. The short-term change in mean performance has a result of -0.8 from year 2018 to 2022. With these results and rankings in international standardized assessments, the Education Commission (EDCOM) II, a group of experts and stakeholders in the Philippine education sector, is committed to working with stakeholders and using empirical data to create a brighter, more meaningful, and more rewarding education system for every Filipino learner (Yee, 2023). Moreover, Yee (2023) highlighted EDCOM II's goal of mitigating and reversing the learning crisis in the Philippine education sector by

implementing effective, data-driven policies that address the root causes of the problem. The persistent Science achievement gap at Grade 4 is a matter of serious concern, particularly in states and schools where Science education is not given as much attention in the elementary grades, as stated by Blank (2013). On the account of this, educators should consider pupils' motivation and the factors that support it when trying to improve the quality of learning experiences and success (Skinner et al., 2017). As Science education is critical to a country's economic growth and development, these skills not only contribute to the formation of a well-prepared workforce of the future, but they also provide individuals with life skills that enable them to thrive (K to 12 Science Curriculum Guide, 2016; NSTA, 2011).

The self-system, which includes pupils' perceptions of their abilities and their motivation to engage in academic tasks, has been widely recognized as a critical determinant of academic success (Bandura, 1997; Ryan & Deci, 2000). Self-system is a network of beliefs and goals, as noted by Marzano and Kendall (2007), that influences one's decisions about whether to engage in a new task. It is also considered as the prime determiner of one's motivation to complete a certain task. An individual will be more driven to complete a task if they believe it is important, has a high chance of success, and will be enjoyable. In contrast, if an individual perceives a task as trivial, likely to fail, or related with a negative emotion that it is unpleasant, then they are less likely to be driven to do it (Marzano & Kendall, 2007).

There were five motivation components which were assessed by Glynn et al., (2011) wherein they investigated the motivation to learn science in college courses. These motivational factors include intrinsic motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, career motivation, and grade motivation. Pupils who demonstrated a strong self-system thinking based on motivation are intrinsically motivated, career-driven, self-determined, self-efficacious, and grade-motivated. These qualities will likely help them to be successful in their academic and professional pursuits.

Pupils with high intrinsic motivation are more likely to be engaged in their learning, persist in the face of challenges, and seek out new knowledge and skills. Conversely, pupils with low intrinsic motivation may struggle to engage in schoolwork, often feeling disengaged and uninterested. This lack of motivation can lead to academic difficulties, as students may not put forth the effort necessary to succeed (Zaiter, 2020).

When pupils have a clear vision for their future and understand the connection between their academic pursuits and their career aspirations, they are more likely to be motivated and engaged in their studies (Negru-Subtirica & Pop, 2016). By fostering career motivation, educators can empower pupils to find purpose and meaning in their education, overcome academic challenges with greater determination, and cultivate the skills and knowledge necessary to pursue their career aspirations.

Pupils who possess high levels of self-determination typically exhibit greater intrinsic motivation, characterized by a genuine eagerness to learn, and comprehend rather than being primarily motivated by external incentives like grades or praise

(Barkoukis et al., 2008). Therefore, giving pupils opportunities to make choices about what and how they learn increases their sense of ownership and engagement.

Pupils with high self-efficacy tend to perceive academic challenges as temporary setbacks rather than insurmountable barriers, as outlined by Margolis and McCabe (2006). This belief in their ability empowers them to find solutions and keep working towards their goals. But pupils who doubt themselves might think they're just not smart enough or capable enough to do well. This can make them feel like giving up because they think they can't change the situation.

Pupils with high grade motivation are more likely to put in the effort and persistence necessary to succeed in their studies. They are willing to spend extra time studying and seek help when needed. The desire to achieve good grades can provide strong determination to overcome challenges like academic difficulties and succeed in their studies. However, it can also lead to negative consequences, such as excessive stress, anxiety, and fear of failure, which can hinder academic performance (Sainio et al., 2019).

Academic difficulties can have a negative impact on pupils' academic achievement, motivation, and self-esteem. Moreover, emotion control of an individual can poorly affect his or her performance in academics (Singh & Singh, 2013). In elementary education, it's important to make sure that pupils learn what they need to know and can do, especially with changes in how learning is delivered.

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has introduced the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) to help plan and teach in all public schools. MELCs were created to help learners get the skills and knowledge they need for the future, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. MELCs help teachers create and give lessons that match the goals and needs of the curriculum. The aim of MELCs is for learners to gain essential competencies and skills for their future success. However, the transition of Grade 4 pupils from primary to intermediate level in public schools complicates the teaching and learning process as well as the medium of instruction (Mercado, 2021).

In the Philippine curriculum context (DepEd, 2019) adherence to the principles and framework of Mother-Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the early grades, the science transition from Grades 3 to 4 has been a problem, most particularly in terms of language used in the teachers and learners' materials including the medium of instruction. The language used from the primary level were in mother tongue or Tagalog contradicting to the English language used in the intermediate level. There is a need to pay attention to the long-term effects of carrying out bilingual process at schools as suggested by Sumardani (2021) before applying it. Filipino third graders' fluency in Science readiness to comprehend and understand fourth level Science which is taught in English were critically explored by Ganeb and Morales (2018) in their study. They determined that the students' difficulties in reading English-language Science texts are attributed to the transition from their native language (L1) to English (L2) as the medium of English are noted as contributing factors to dysfluency.

Moreover, when parents have negative attitudes toward Science education, it correlates with lower Science achievement in their children, and vice versa. This indicates that parental support plays a significant role in shaping a pupil's performance (Chohan & Khan, 2010; Perera, 2014).

Therefore, a positive self-system encourages learners to approach challenges with confidence, perseverance, and enthusiasm, while a negative self-system may lead to self-doubt and reluctance to engage with academic content (Pajares & Schunk, 2005).

Caymaz and Aydin (2021) found out in the conducted study for secondary school learners that there was a significant relationship between learners' Science motivation and academic achievement.

Academic achievement is believed to be the most significant result of formal education. In the implementation of Philippines K-12 curriculum, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued the DepEd Order no. 8, series of 2015. The policy is about the guidelines on classroom assessment for the K-12 Basic Education Program which allows teachers to monitor and evaluate learners' progress. The DepEd Order no. 8 provides a guide about the grading system and how to compute the grades where learners may be assessed through the following process whether formative or summative. The components of summative assessment are written works, performance task, and quarterly assessment. The sum of each component for the weighted score will serve as the initial grade then transmuted using the transmutation table prescribed by DepEd. The transmuted grade is reflected in the report card. During the parent-teacher conferences, the teachers show the learners' progress to their parents and guardians, reporting the grades with the certain descriptors for every corresponding grading scale which indicates whether a pupil has passed or failed remark.

Although this is undeniably important, researchers and policymakers are increasingly turning to social and emotional factors as well as the relationships among them as indicators of students' psychological development and well-being (Kell et al., 2013; Moore, 2019).

In the study conducted by Patrick et al. (2007) they concluded that motivation has a great influence on learner's achievement in Science. Those pupils who are motivated to learn Science can perform significantly better than those unmotivated.

Also, in the study conducted by Cavas (2011) for primary learners from sixth to eighth grades, it was found that motivation had a considerable impact towards learning Science leading to a more positive attitude and higher scores on Science achievement tests.

Despite its importance, there is a notable lack of research focusing on the interplay between Grade 4 pupils' self-system and the academic difficulties they face in Science education. Understanding this relationship is crucial for educators aiming to develop more effective instructional strategies and interventions tailored to the needs of Grade 4 pupils.

Such insights could foster a love for Science and lead to improved academic performance.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study is based on the participants' self-system thinking, which is categorized into different types of motivation. These include intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation. The study also examined the participants' perceived academic difficulties based on the most essential learning competencies in Science 4. Academic achievement in Science 4 is measured through performance tasks, written works, and quarterly examinations.

Self-system thinking is a theoretical framework that entails assessing and examining an individual's drive to engage in learning new material. In other words, it is understanding how one's own thoughts and feelings influence one's desire to learn new things (Marzano & Kendall, 2008). As stated by Vázquez-Villegas et al. (2023), it is the primary level of learner's engagement which consists of attitudes, beliefs and emotions that determine their motivation whether they take part in or not in each task. Moreover, motivation is the desire to engage in an activity (Clarke & Hennig, 2013; Smith et al., 2013).

Concisely, self-system thinking based on motivation means examining how a person's thoughts and emotions impact their eagerness to learn new things. It is essentially about figuring out what motivates an individual to engage in a task. The performance of Grade 4 pupils in Science is influenced by a multitude of factors namely: intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation. These categories of self-system thinking based on motivation plays an important role in pupils' ability to overcome academic difficulties (Glynn et al., 2011).

Intrinsic motivation is the desire to engage in an activity for its own sake rather than for external rewards (Sansone & Harackiewicz, 2000; Lee et al., 2012). This is evident in the enjoyment of the learning process and the willingness to go beyond what was required to do. For example, some pupils spend time outside of class working on projects and assignments because they find the material interesting and challenging. Intrinsic motivation is consistently positively associated with academic achievement and satisfaction (Taylor et al., 2014; Buzdar et al., 2017).

Career motivation, the desire to pursue a particular career path (Razali et al., 2020), can play a significant role in helping pupils overcome academic difficulties. Shin et al. (2016) found out in their study that career motivation plays a crucial role in Science learning and predicts learners' STEM track choice. This was evident in their focus on acquiring the skills and knowledge they needed to be successful in their chosen fields (Aeschlimann et al., 2016). For example, some of the learners may take on internships and volunteer positions in their fields of interest.

Self-determination, which is the belief that individuals have control over their own lives and can make their own choices, emphasize the importance of their innate

psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Jayarathne & Chandrasena, 2020; Ryan et al., 2021). According to Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2015), when these needs are met, individuals are more likely to feel self-determined and motivated to engage in activities that are meaningful to them (Jang et al., 2016). This can be evident in the ability of the pupils to set their own goals and take initiative in their learning. For example, some pupils may come up with their own research projects and work independently to complete them.

Self-efficacy, a concept developed by psychologist Albert Bandura (1997), is the belief that an individual has the capability to achieve their goals (Bandura, 1997; Donkoh, 2023; Ootim 2000). In academics, self-efficacy plays a crucial role in motivation and learning, and educators should address pupils' beliefs to provide more engaging and effective instruction (Artino, 2012). This can be evident if learners are confident in their abilities and have their willingness to take risks. For example, some of the pupils participated in challenging projects and assignments, even though they were not sure they would be successful.

Grade motivation is the desire to get good grades. This can be evident when the learners focus on completing assignments and studying for exams (Immerwahr, 2011). Grade motivation can be both helpful and harmful to academic achievement. Pupils who are motivated by grades may be more likely to put in the effort and persistence necessary to succeed. However, they may also experience excessive stress and anxiety, which can hinder their performance. Furthermore, it is important to note that grade motivation was not the primary motivator for an individual (Koenka et al., 2019). They were more motivated by intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, and self-efficacy.

Academic difficulties are a common problem for learners of all ages (Kazmi & Pervez, 2010), but they can be especially challenging for Grade 4 pupils in Science. This is because Science is a subject that requires a strong foundation in prior knowledge, as well as the ability to think critically and solve problems. In the Philippines during the pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) has introduced the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) to ensure learners gain the knowledge and skills they need for the future, regardless of how learning is delivered which is used until now. However, few studies have focused on the development of MELCs as a strategic approach to modular learning (Gabriel et al., 2022). The main issue is that the essential learning competencies in Science have been negatively affected, particularly in the context of modular learning during the pandemic. This is because learners have not fully grasped the fundamental concepts in the subject, which are necessary for mastering current and future competencies, most especially in their previous year level.

The learners' difficulties in learning new Science concepts can be attributed to their struggles with previous topics that are crucial to understanding the current lesson as stated by Gabriel et al. (2022). This issue has been exacerbated by the sudden shift to modular learning, which has resulted in a significant gap between learners and the new mode of instruction. The inquiry results support these claims, as they show that the shift to modular learning has decreased the effectiveness of instruction delivery due to a lack

of preparatory measures, insufficient teacher support, and the inadequacy of the modality to process Science concepts. In addition, as stated by Mercado (2021), the mode of teaching and learning process due to the transition from Grade 3 in Tagalog to Grade 4 in English elevates the difficulty level. Bernardo et al. (2008) suggested that when educational institutions attempt to enhance the structure and implementation of Science curricula, it may be beneficial to consider the perspectives of Science learners. When pupils face challenges in learning or achieving academic success, these difficulties can range from mild to severe and can affect any subject area.

Academic difficulties can be discouraging, leading to decreased motivation, engagement, and effort. This creates a vicious cycle where low motivation further exacerbates existing difficulties. Persistent struggles can negatively impact self-esteem and confidence, creating anxiety or fear of failure that can further hinder academic achievement.

Academic achievement refers to the result of the educational process, which reflects how well a learner, teacher, or institution has met their educational objectives which is typically evaluated through exams or ongoing assessments (Narula & Sindhvani, 2016). In the Philippine context, the K to 12 curriculum classroom assessment is guided by the DepEd Order no. 8, series 2015. It has two types of assessment: the formative and the summative. Formative assessment may be administered by the teachers to modify their instructions and check learner's progress to assist them in determining their strengths and weaknesses. This can be done before, during, and after the lesson proper. On the other hand, summative assessment takes place at the end of a quarter or period of learning which determines and evaluates the learning standard obtained by the learner. As a basis for grading, summative assessment focuses on three components: written work, performance task, and quarterly assessment.

Written work (WW) is one of the assessment tools used by DepEd in the Philippines to gauge learners' learning progress, measures a learner's understanding of concepts and application of skills in written form such as long tests and quizzes for practice and preparation on quarterly assessments.

Performance Task (PT) is a specific type of assessment tool used to gauge a learner's ability to apply their knowledge and skills by displaying what they know and exhibiting them in various ways such as oral work, group presentations and projects. A scoring guide or rubric is used that gives criteria for assessment and how a learner's work will be evaluated.

Quarterly Assessment (QA) is administered at the end of each academic quarter which synthesizes all the learning skills, concepts, and values learned. Scores on quarterly assessments typically contribute to a learner's overall grade for the quarter.

According to the policy of DepEd Order no.8, series 2015, all grades depend on the learner's weighted raw score on the summative assessment which states that the minimum passing grade in learning areas is 60 or equal to 75 on the report card. In every

grading, the teacher will compute all the scores from the learner’s written work, performance task and quarterly assessment. These three components are given specific percentage weights that vary according to the nature of the learning area. For Grade 4 Science, the weight of the components is 40% for the written work, 40% for the performance task, and 20% for the quarterly assessment.

Although grades and standardized tests are frequently used to gauge success, it's important to understand that achievement is a complicated idea with many facets and contributing factors. Furthermore, it is complex and should consider individual pupils' personal perspective, expectations, and motivation (Guterman, 2020). Grades, test scores, completion of degrees or certifications are common metrics while learning styles, motivations, prior experiences, and personal circumstances significantly impact individual achievement. Pupils who have higher levels of self-awareness, self-regulation, and self-efficacy are more likely to be intrinsically motivated, set realistic goals, and persist in the face of challenges.

Figure 1 shows that self-system thinking based on motivation may help pupils overcome academic difficulties leading to increased resilience, perseverance, and problem-solving skills which can ultimately contribute to academic achievement in the long run.

Figure 1. Relationship between Self-System Thinking based on Motivation, Academic Achievement, and Academic Difficulties Encountered by Pupils in Science 4

Research Questions

This study aimed to measure the relationship between self-system thinking based on motivation, academic achievement, and academic difficulties encountered by pupils in Science 4.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Intrinsic Motivation,
 - 1.2. Career Motivation,
 - 1.3. Self-Determination,
 - 1.4. Self-Efficacy, and
 - 1.5. Grade Motivation?
2. How may the academic difficulties encountered by the participants in Science 4 be described?
3. How may the academic achievement of the participants in Science 4 be described based on:
 - 3.1. Performance Task,
 - 3.2. Written Works, and
 - 3.3. Quarterly Examinations?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and their academic achievement in Science 4?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' academic achievement and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4?
7. What are the implications of the result of the study in enhancing the academic achievement of the learners in Science education?

Null Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the researchers formulated the following hypothesis:

- H₀1. There is no significant correlations between participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4.
- H₀2. There is no significant correlations between participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and their academic achievement in Science 4.
- H₀3. There is no significant correlations between participants' academic achievement and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive-correlational research design. It is descriptive because it describes the self-system thinking of the Filipino fourth graders based on motivation, their academic achievement, and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4. It is correlational because it aimed to determine the relationship between the self-system thinking, academic difficulties, and the academic achievement of the Grade 4 pupils.

A total enumeration was employed in the selection of the participants of this study. They were the 201 Grade 4 pupils enrolled during the school year 2023-2024 in a government-owned elementary school in the Philippines. All 201 pupils or 100% of the population were able to participate.

This study utilized primarily the Science Motivation Questionnaire II (SMQ-II) developed by Glynn (2011) to measure self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants. It was adapted as the main instrument in gathering the data. The questionnaire has 25 items focused on the motivation to learn science. The statements are easy to read which can be completed efficiently in about 15 minutes.

According to the findings of Glynn et al., (2011), the questionnaire is reliable, valid, and efficient as a tool for assessing components of students' motivation to learn Science. These items were pilot tested with samples of Science majors ($n = 31$) and non-Science majors ($n = 34$) in their study. To ensure its validity and reliability and to know if the questions are applicable for the level of elementary students, the questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing at Mining Elementary School. It was tested to their Grade 4 level with 30 pupils ($n = 30$) who participated with the consent of the parents. Questions were translated from English to Filipino language to express the sense of its words and phrases and it was completed for only 10 minutes. Based on the pilot testing result, the questionnaire for the Science Motivation Questionnaire II (SMQ-II) with 25 items yielded a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = .889$ which indicates that the items have high internal consistency and reliability.

The Science Motivation Questionnaire II (SMQ-II) items are associated with the factors on intrinsic motivation (items 1, 3, 12, 17, and 19); career motivation (items 7, 10, 13, 23 and 25); self-determination (items 5, 6, 11, 16 and 22); self-efficacy (items 9, 14, 15, 18 and 21); grade motivation (items 2, 4, 8, 20, and 24). The correlations among the represented factors are considered correct and viewed as true association among the motivation components. All the 25 items have Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.92$ (Glynn et al., 2011). One statement was slightly modified so that it would be more appropriate for the Grade 4 level context. Pupils responded to each item on a rating scale of temporal frequency: never (0), rarely (1), sometimes (2), often (3), or always (4).

The second device was the Academic Difficulties in Learning Science Questionnaire, a researcher's made tool wherein the statements were based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). This tool was validated by the experts. The

DepEd MELCs are rephrased and identified learning competencies which were the most crucial for achieving content and performance standards. These competencies were highlighted and implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic as part of the education department's Learning Continuity Plan and will still be implemented up to the year 2024 before Matatag Curriculum will be administered.

A Likert four-point scale of knowledge-difficulty levels type question was designed to be used to receive feedback from respondents about the Most Essential Learning Competencies in Science 4 from 1st to 2nd quarter only. The questionnaire has 12 items focused on the most essential learning competencies in Science 4.

The instrument was subjected for pilot testing. The responses were analyzed with an SPSS statistics program showing that questionnaire for the Academic Difficulties in Learning Science with 12 items has a result of Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = .847$ which indicates that the items have high internal consistency and reliability.

The data collected from 201 participants using Google Form was transposed into MS Excel. The data were given appropriate numerical code then transposed into Licensed IBM SPSS Statistics version 25 for statistical treatment and analysis.

The mean (μ) and standard deviation (sd) were used in describing the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation with the μ range and description as follows:

<u>μ Range</u>	<u>Description</u>
3.50 - 4.00	Always
2.50 - 3.49	Often
1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes
0.50 - 1.49	Rarely
0.00 - 0.49	Never

The mean (μ) and standard deviation (sd) were used in describing the participants' level of academic difficulties encountered in Science 4 with the μ range and description as follows:

<u>μ Range</u>	<u>Description</u>
3.50 - 4.00	Very Difficult
2.50 - 3.49	Difficult
1.50 - 2.49	Easy
0.00 - 1.49	Very Easy

The frequency (f), percentage (%), mean (μ), standard deviation (sd), median (med) and interquartile range (IQR) were used in describing the respondents' level of academic achievements in Science 4 based on the first and second quarter total general weighted average (GWA) in terms of their written works, performance task and quarterly examination presented based on these scales and description as prescribed by DepEd

Order No. 8 s. 2015 Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program as follows:

Academic Performance	Description
below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectations
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
80% - 84%	Satisfactory
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
90% - 100%	Outstanding

To test the significant relationship between the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants, their academic difficulties encountered in Science 4, and the academic achievement in Science 4, the Spearman's rho was used. The p-value less than or equal to .05 is considered significant.

The strength of correlation by Dancy and Reidy (2004) was utilized to interpret the obtained correlation coefficient value:

<u>Correlation Coefficient Value</u>	<u>Direction and Strength of Correlation</u>
1.00	Perfect (+/-) correlation
0.70 to 0.99	Strong (+/-) correlation
0.40 to 0.69	Moderate (+/-) correlation
0.10 to 0.39	Weak (+/-) correlation
0.00 to 0.09	No correlation

RESULTS

The data gathered were organized and processed using the appropriate statistical tools and techniques which revealed the following results:

Participants' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation

Table 1 shows the result of analysis of the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation.

Intrinsic motivation. The results revealed that the participants often enjoyed learning Science ($\mu = 3.02$, $sd = 1.24$); think that the Science they learned is relevant to their lives ($\mu = 2.87$, $sd = 1.17$); curious about discoveries in Science ($\mu = 2.79$, $sd = 1.21$); think that learning Science is interesting ($\mu = 2.78$, $sd = 1.38$); and it makes their lives more meaningful ($\mu = 2.53$, $sd = 1.38$). In general, the participants often ($\mu = 2.77$, $sd = 0.84$) are intrinsically motivated in learning Science.

Career motivation. The results showed that the participants often believed that learning Science will help them get a good job ($\mu = 3.21$, $sd = 1.13$); think that

understanding Science will benefit them in their career ($\mu = 3.00$, $sd = 1.28$); also for them, knowing Science will give them a job in the future advantage ($\mu = 2.93$, $sd = 1.17$); anticipate that they will use Science problem-solving skills in my job in the future ($\mu = 2.66$, $sd = 1.27$); and expect their future job will involve Science ($\mu = 2.54$, $sd = 1.26$). In general, the participants often ($\mu = 2.87$, $sd = 0.86$) are career motivated when learning Science.

Self-determination. The analysis of the data revealed that the participants often put enough effort into learning Science ($\mu = 3.28$, $sd = 1.05$); study hard to learn Science ($\mu = 3.11$, $sd = 1.16$); prepare well for Science tests and labs ($\mu = 2.90$, $sd = 1.17$); use strategies to learn Science well ($\mu = 2.80$, $sd = 1.21$); and spend a lot of time learning Science ($\mu = 2.60$, $sd = 1.35$). In general, the participants often ($\mu = 2.92$, $sd = 0.87$) are self-determined to learn Science.

Self-efficacy. From the data, the results revealed that the participants often were confident that they will do well on Science tests ($\mu = 3.00$, $sd = 1.18$); are confident that they will do well on Science labs and projects ($\mu = 2.90$, $sd = 1.21$); believe they can master Science knowledge and skills ($\mu = 2.86$, $sd = 1.22$); believe that they can earn a grade of "97-100" in Science ($\mu = 2.83$, $sd = 1.21$); and are sure that they can understand Science that is being taught using the English language ($\mu = 2.72$, $sd = 1.27$). In general, the participants often ($\mu = 2.84$, $sd = 0.92$) have the sense of self-efficacy when learning Science.

Grade motivation. The results revealed that the participants often thought getting a good Science grade is important to them ($\mu = 3.11$, $sd = 1.10$); believe that it is important that they get a grade of "97-100" in Science ($\mu = 3.00$, $sd = 1.12$); furthermore, scoring high on Science tests and labs matters to them ($\mu = 2.90$, $sd = 1.20$); think about the grade they will get in Science ($\mu = 2.85$, $sd = 1.21$); and they like to do better than other students on Science tests ($\mu = 2.63$, $sd = 1.30$). In general, the participants often ($\mu = 2.92$, $sd = 0.90$) are motivated with their grades in learning Science.

Table 1

Participants' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation

Intrinsic Motivation	N	R	S	O	A	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
1. The Science I learn is relevant to my life.	10	21	29	66	75	2.87	1.17	Often
2. Learning Science is interesting.	21	21	30	38	91	2.78	1.38	Often
3. Learning Science makes my life more meaningful.	25	28	28	55	65	2.53	1.38	Often
4. I am curious about discoveries in Science.	13	17	45	50	76	2.79	1.21	Often
5. I enjoy learning Science.	11	21	24	42	103	3.02	1.24	Often
<i>Sub-mean</i>						2.77	0.84	Often

Table 1 (Continuation)

Career Motivation	N	R	S	O	A	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
6. Learning Science will help me get a good job.	8	13	25	38	117	3.21	1.13	Often
7. Knowing Science will give me a job in the future advantage.	10	17	34	57	83	2.93	1.17	Often
8. Understanding Science will benefit me in my career.	18	13	18	55	97	3.00	1.28	Often
9. My future job will involve Science.	17	28	41	60	55	2.54	1.26	Often
10. I will use Science problem-solving skills in my job in the future.	17	20	46	49	69	2.66	1.27	Often
<i>Sub-mean</i>						2.87	0.86	Often
Self-Determination	N	R	S	O	A	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
11. I put enough effort into learning Science.	6	10	24	42	119	3.28	1.05	Often
12. I use strategies to learn Science well.	12	26	22	72	69	2.80	1.21	Often
13. I spend a lot of time learning Science.	25	16	42	50	68	2.60	1.35	Often
14. I prepare well for Science tests and labs.	8	24	29	59	81	2.90	1.17	Often
15. I study hard to learn Science.	8	17	26	43	107	3.11	1.16	Often
<i>Sub-mean</i>						2.92	0.87	Often
Self-efficacy	N	R	S	O	A	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
16. I am confident I will do well on Science tests.	10	16	31	50	94	3.00	1.18	Often
17. I am confident I will do well on Science labs and projects.	12	19	30	56	84	2.90	1.21	Often
18. I believe I can master Science knowledge and skills.	12	19	37	51	82	2.86	1.22	Often
19. I believe I can earn a grade of "97-100" in Science.	14	14	41	55	77	2.83	1.21	Often
20. I am sure I can understand Science that is being taught using the English language.	15	22	42	48	74	2.72	1.27	Often
<i>Sub-mean</i>						2.84	0.92	Often

Table 1 (Continuation)

Grade Motivation	N	R	S	O	A	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
21. I like to do better than other students on Science tests.	21	16	48	48	68	2.63	1.30	Often
22. Getting a good Science grade is important to me.	5	20	23	52	101	3.11	1.10	Often
23. It is important that I get a grade of "97-100" in Science.	5	21	35	49	91	3.00	1.12	Often
24. I think about the grade I will get in Science.	15	12	39	57	78	2.85	1.21	Often
25. Scoring high on Science tests and labs matters to me.	11	17	40	46	87	2.90	1.20	Often
<i>Sub-mean</i>						2.92	0.90	Often
<i>Overall Mean</i>						2.86	0.87	Often

N = 201; N = Never (0-0.49), R = Rarely (.50-1.49), S = Sometimes (1.50-2.49), O = Often (2.50-3.49), A = Always (3.50-4.00)
 μ = mean, *sd* = standard deviation, desc = description

Academic Difficulties Encountered by the Participants in Science 4

The results of the analysis of the academic difficulties encountered by the participants in Science 4 are presented in Table 2. The results showed that the participants have not encountered difficulties in studying Science 4 in the first quarter as they rated all indicators as easy. These indicators are identifying changes in materials whether useful or harmful to one's environment ($\mu = 2.17$, *sd* = .92); describing changes in properties of materials when exposed to certain conditions such as temperature or when mixed with other materials ($\mu = 2.16$, *sd* = .88); classifying materials based on the ability to absorb water, float, sink, undergo decay ($\mu = 2.15$, *sd* = .88); and describing changes in solid materials when they are bent, pressed, hammered, or cut ($\mu = 2.11$, *sd* = .82).

In addition, the results showed that the participants have not encountered difficulties in studying Science 4 in the second quarter as they rated all indicators as easy. These indicators are describing the effect of the environment on the life cycle of organisms ($\mu = 2.34$, *sd* = .88); describe some types of beneficial interactions among living things ($\mu = 2.31$, *sd* = .97); describe the effects of interactions among organism in their environment ($\mu = 2.30$, *sd* = 1.03); inferring that body structures help animals adapt and survive in their particular habitat ($\mu = 2.29$, *sd* = .96); comparing the stages in the life cycle of organisms ($\mu = 2.18$, *sd* = 1); describing the main function of the major organs ($\mu = 2.14$, *sd* = .87); identifying the specialized structures of terrestrial and aquatic plants ($\mu = 2.07$, *sd* = .92); and communicating that the major organs work together to make the body function properly ($\mu = 2.03$, *sd* = .87).

In general, the participants have the overall ratings of $\mu = 2.18$ with *sd* = .60 of academic difficulties. This implied that the participants have not encountered difficulties in studying Science 4 subject.

Table 2*Academic Difficulties Encountered by the Participants in Science 4*

MELCs in Science 4 (1st Quarter)	VE	E	D	VD	μ	<i>sd</i>	Desc
1. Classifying materials based on the ability to absorb water, float, sink, undergo decay.	52	80	56	13	2.15	0.88	Easy
2. Describing changes in solid materials when they are bent, pressed, hammered, or cut.	49	91	51	10	2.11	0.82	Easy
3. Describing changes in properties of materials when exposed to certain conditions such as temperature or when mixed with other materials.	48	90	46	17	2.16	0.88	Easy
4. Identifying changes in materials whether useful or harmful to one's environment.	50	87	43	21	2.17	0.92	Easy
MELCs in Science 4 (2nd Quarter)	VE	E	D	VD	μ	<i>Sd</i>	Desc
5. Describing the main function of the major organs.	49	90	46	16	2.14	0.87	Easy
6. Communicating that the major organs work together to make the body function properly.	59	92	35	15	2.03	0.87	Easy
7. Inferring that body structures help animals adapt and survive in their particular habitat.	53	56	72	20	2.29	0.96	Easy
8. Identifying the specialized structures of terrestrial and aquatic plants.	61	82	40	18	2.07	0.92	Easy
9. Comparing the stages in the life cycle of organisms.	62	65	50	24	2.18	1.00	Easy
10. Describing the effect of the environment on the life cycle of organisms.	33	89	56	23	2.34	0.88	Easy
11. Describe some types of beneficial interactions among living things.	45	77	50	29	2.31	0.97	Easy
12. Describe the effects of interactions among organism in their environment.	53	68	47	33	2.30	1.03	Easy
<i>Sub-mean</i>					2.18	0.60	Easy

*N = 201; VE = Very Easy (1.00-1.49), E = Easy (1.50-2.49), D = Difficult (2.50-3.49), VD = Very Difficult (3.50-4.00)
 μ = mean, *sd* = standard deviation, desc = description*

Academic Achievement of the Participants in Science 4

The academic achievement of the participants is presented in Table 3. Most of the respondents have an academic performance of satisfactory with a grade of 80% - 84% (70 or 34.8%), followed by a very satisfactory achievement with a grade of 85% to 89%

(50 or 24.9%), and an academic achievement of outstanding with a grade of 90%-100% (40 or 19.9%). On the other hand, 30 or 14.9% of the respondents with academic performance of fairly satisfactory and with academic performance of did not meet expectations (11 or 5.5%). The overall academic performance of the respondents has a median of 84 and an interquartile range of ± 8 which showed the dispersion of the grades of the respondents from 76 to 92 with a description of fairly satisfactory to outstanding.

In addition, the biggest percentage of academic achievement of the participants was from the performance tasks which is 40% of the academic achievement and has a mean of 34.51 and standard deviation of 4.84, followed by the written works which is 40% of the academic achievement and has a mean of 28.03 and standard deviation of 5.84.

However, the lowest percentage of academic achievement of the participants was from the quarterly examination which is 20% of the academic achievement and has a mean of 12.17 and standard deviation of 3.69.

Table 3

Participants' Academic Achievement in Science 4

Academic Achievement	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (90 – 100)	40	19.9
Very Satisfactory (85 – 89)	50	24.9
Satisfactory (80 – 84)	70	34.8
Fairly Satisfactory (75 – 79)	30	14.9
Did Not Meet Expectation (Below 75)	11	5.5
Total	201	100.0
Median	84.00	
Interquartile Range	± 8.00	
Components of Grades	Mean	SD
Performance Tasks	34.51	± 4.84
Written Works	28.03	± 5.84
Quarterly Examination	12.17	± 3.69
GWA	83.97	± 5.71

Relationship between the Participants' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation and Their Academic Difficulties They Encounter in Science 4

The result of the Spearman's rho test of correlation between the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science 4 is presented in Table 4.

The p -value revealed significant relationship between the academic difficulties and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of self-efficacy ($p = .048$, $r = -.140$) with 95% confidence level, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The *correlation coefficient* (r) indicates that the correlation is weak and negative. The result indicates that the academic difficulties of the participants seem lower when their self-efficacy is higher. However, the weak degree of correlation indicated that self-efficacy accounts for only little variation and there are other variables that are more correlated to their academic difficulties.

However, the p -value revealed no significant relationship between the academic difficulties and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of intrinsic motivation ($p = .772$, $r = -.021$), career motivation ($p = .110$, $r = -.113$), self-determination ($p = .381$, $r = -.062$), and grade motivation ($p = .455$, $r = -.053$), thus the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected. The result indicates that the academic difficulties of the participants have no correlation in their self-system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, and grade motivation.

Table 4

Relationship between Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation and the Academic Difficulties in Science 4

Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation	Academic Difficulties in Science 4		
	r	p value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	-0.021	0.772	No Correlation
Career Motivation	-0.113	0.110	No Correlation
Self-Determination	-0.062	0.381	No Correlation
Self-Efficacy	-.140*	0.048	Weak-Negative Correlation
Grade Motivation	-0.053	0.455	No Correlation

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on Motivation and Their Academic Achievement in Science 4

The result of the Spearman's rho test of correlation between the participants' self-system thinking based on motivation and their academic achievement in Science 4 in terms of written works, performance task, quarterly examination, and grade weighted average in Science 4 is presented in Table 5.

Written works. The result showed no significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of written works and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of intrinsic motivation ($p = .854$, $r = -.013$), career motivation ($p = .412$, $r = -.058$), self-determination ($p = .960$, $r = .004$), self-efficacy ($p = .580$, $r = .039$), and grade motivation ($p = .352$, $r = -.066$), thus the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected. The result indicates that the academic achievement in terms of written works of the participants has no correlation with their self-system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation.

Performance tasks. The p -value revealed significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of performance tasks and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of self-efficacy ($p = .045$, $r = .142$), and grade motivation ($p = .005$, $r = .199$), thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The *correlation coefficient* (r) indicates that the correlation is weak and positive. The result indicates that the academic achievement of the participants in terms of performance tasks seem higher, when their self-efficacy and grade motivation are higher. However, the weak degree of correlation indicated that self-efficacy and grade motivation account for only little variation and there are other variables that are more correlated to their academic achievement in terms of performance tasks.

However, the result showed no significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of performance tasks and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of intrinsic motivation ($p = .215$, $r = .088$), career motivation ($p = .112$, $r = .112$), and self-determination ($p = .197$, $r = .091$), thus the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected. The result indicates that the academic achievement in terms of performance tasks of the participants has no correlation with their self-system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, and self-determination.

Quarterly examination. The result showed no significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of quarterly examination and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of intrinsic motivation ($p = .089$, $r = .120$), career motivation ($p = .921$, $r = .007$), self-determination ($p = .764$, $r = .021$), self-efficacy ($p = .248$, $r = .082$), and grade motivation ($p = .539$, $r = .044$), thus the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected. The result indicates that the academic achievement in terms of quarterly examination of the participants have no correlation in their self-system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation.

Grade weighted average. The result showed no significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of grade weighted average and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the participants in terms of intrinsic motivation ($p = .225$, $r = .086$), career motivation ($p = .611$, $r = .036$), self-determination ($p = .308$, $r = .072$), self-efficacy ($p = .113$, $r = .112$), and grade motivation ($p = .266$, $r = .079$), thus the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected. The result indicates that the academic achievement in terms of grade weighted average of the participants has no correlation in their self-

system thinking based on motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation.

Table 5

Relationship between the Participants' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation and Their Academic Achievement in Science 4

Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation	Academic Achievement in Science 4		
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	-0.013	0.854	No Correlation
Career Motivation	-0.058	0.412	No Correlation
Self-Determination	0.004	0.960	No Correlation
Self-Efficacy	0.039	0.580	No Correlation
Grade Motivation	-0.066	0.352	No Correlation
Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation	Performance Tasks		
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	0.088	0.215	No Correlation
Career Motivation	0.112	0.112	No Correlation
Self-Determination	0.091	0.197	No Correlation
Self-Efficacy	.142*	0.045	Weak-positive Correlation
Grade Motivation	.199**	0.005	Weak-positive Correlation
Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation	Quarterly Examination		
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	0.120	0.089	No Correlation
Career Motivation	0.007	0.921	No Correlation
Self-Determination	0.021	0.764	No Correlation
Self-Efficacy	0.082	0.248	No Correlation
Grade Motivation	0.044	0.539	No Correlation

Table 5 (Continuation)

Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation	General Weighted Average		
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	0.086	0.225	No Correlation
Career Motivation	0.036	0.611	No Correlation
Self-Determination	0.072	0.308	No Correlation
Self-Efficacy	0.112	0.113	No Correlation

Grade Motivation	0.079	0.266	No Correlation
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*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Relationship between the Participants' Academic Achievement and the Academic Difficulties they Encounter in Science 4

The result of the Spearman's rho test of correlation between the participants' academic achievement and the academic difficulties they encountered in Science 4 is presented in Table 6.

The result revealed a significant relationship between the academic difficulties and the academic achievement in terms of written works ($p = .016$, $r = -.169$) with 95% confidence level, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The *correlation coefficient* (r) indicates that the correlation is weak and negative. The result indicates that the academic difficulties of the participants seem higher, when their academic achievement in terms of written works is lower. However, the weak degree of correlation indicated that the written works accounts for only little variation and there are other variables that are more correlated to their academic difficulties.

However, the p -value revealed no significant relationship between the academic difficulties and the academic achievement of the participants in terms of performance tasks ($p = .642$, $r = .033$), quarterly examination ($p = .383$, $r = -.062$), and grade weighted average ($p = .303$, $r = -.073$). The result indicates that the academic difficulties of the participants have no correlation in their academic achievement in terms of performance tasks, quarterly examination, and grade weighted average.

Table 6

Relationship between Academic Achievement and the Academic Difficulties in Science 4

Academic Achievement	Academic Difficulties		
	r	p value	Interpretation
Written Works	-.169*	0.016	Weak-negative Correlation
Performance Tasks	0.033	0.642	No Correlation
Quarterly Examination	-0.062	0.383	No Correlation
GWA	-0.073	0.303	No Correlation

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

This study explored the relationship between self-system thinking based on intrinsic, career, self-determination, self-efficacy, grade motivation, academic achievement in terms of written works, performance tasks, quarterly examinations, and the academic difficulties encountered in the subject Science among Grade 4 pupils.

Participants' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation

Marzano and Kendall's work in self-system thinking, particularly concerning motivation, contributes significantly to the understanding of how individuals regulate their behavior and achieve their goals (Marzano & Kendall, 2007). In the present study, results showed that the Grade 4 pupils, in general, are often motivated to learn Science, indicating that this occurs frequently. These motivational factors, namely, intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation, all point to a high level of motivation among the pupils.

Among the five motivational factors of pupils' self-system thinking, both grade motivation and self-determination are rated the highest. Therefore, most pupils were often driven by the desire to attain good grades and have a sense of self-determination. For pupils, having an outstanding grade is important including having high scores on their tests and labs. On that account, pupils who are driven by grades frequently devote enough time and energy in learning Science. They are motivated and self-assured to work hard in their studies and prepare for Science exams and laboratories (Jang et al., 2016). It is evident that pupil's self-determination is the primary motivator of grade motivation as they set their own goals and take initiative in their learning as explained by Koenka et al. (2019). Self-determination is closely linked to the concept of intrinsic motivation, as it allows pupils to feel in control of their own behavior and decision-making. This sense of autonomy can help them feel more engaged and motivated in their activities (Barkoukis et al., 2008).

However, intrinsic motivation ranks below the other aspects. This might indicate that the pupils are not naturally interested in Science. On the contrary, this result contradicts to the study of the Chandran and Awang (2023), wherein the most dominant factor for primary pupils is the intrinsic motivation in learning. Despite the result, it is still positive to indicate that the pupils are also often motivated due to their interest and enjoyment in the Science task, suggesting that they tend to find science activities somewhat enjoyable and engaging for their own sake.

Overall, the five categories of motivations: intrinsic, career, self-determination, self-efficacy, and grade motivation play important roles to pupils' self-system thinking which centers around the idea that pupils are active participants in their own motivation and

learning processes (Marzano & Kendall, 2007), and can work together to create a positive and engaging learning environment, developing a lifelong love in learning Science.

Academic Difficulties Encountered by the Participants in Science 4

In terms of the academic difficulties encountered by pupils in Science 4, the identified most essential learning competencies for the 1st and 2nd quarters only, were generally assessed and rated as “Easy” to achieve. This indicates that most pupils found it easy to accomplish the MELCs in both quarters. There can be a positive connection between these difficulties and pupils' motivation in terms of grades and self-determination which can be closely connected to their ease of learning Science.

Marzano and Kendall (2008) examined how individuals attribute success and failure, and how these attributions impact motivation. They argue that individuals who attribute success to internal factors (e.g., effort, ability) and failure to external factors (e.g., task difficulty, luck) are more likely to maintain motivation and persist in the face of challenges (Marzano & Kendall, 2008). In short, if pupils think they do well because they tried hard or they're good at it, they're more likely to keep trying even when things get tough. On the other hand, if pupils blame failure on things like the task being too hard or just plain luck, they might feel less motivated to keep trying (Singh & Singh, 2013).

Therefore, the pupils may struggle but still develop strong self-determination through overcoming challenges. They are willing to spend extra time studying, seek help when needed, and persevere in the face of challenges with the desire to achieve good grades in Science.

Participants' Academic Achievement in Science 4

The grades of the pupils ranging from 76 to 92 have a description of fairly satisfactory to outstanding, which is encouraging. This indicates that most pupils are performing well academically in Science.

Interestingly, the biggest percentage of academic achievement comes from performance tasks, which accounts for 40% of the academic achievement. They are engaging, rigorous, and relevant, making them more effective than traditional review methods. When pupils are actively involved in the learning process, they are more likely to retain the information, and performance tasks are an effective way to do so. However, it contradicts to the result of the study of Albalate et al. (2018) wherein performance goal was found to be the least influential factor for Grade 11 learners. This suggests that for Grade 4 pupils, performance tasks are a valuable tool for assessing their learning, as they require to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world contexts. On the contrary, quarterly examination, which accounts for 20%, has the lowest percentage of academic achievement. Despite having a lower mean score, the Quarterly Examination has less influence on the overall grade due to its 20% weight. This indicates that it might be a more

challenging component for pupils, but its lesser impact on the final grade mitigates this difficulty to some extent.

The complexity of questions for the Quarterly Examination might include more higher order thinking questions compared to Written Works and Performance Tasks. It likely covers a wider range of topics, requiring comprehensive understanding and retention of material from the entire quarter.

Pupils might not prepare adequately for the Quarterly Examination due to poor study habits or lack of effective revision strategies. Since the exam covers content from the entire quarter, pupils who have not kept up with regular study and review may find it challenging. Also, pupils may struggle to manage their time effectively during the exam, leading to incomplete answers.

Addressing these potential factors and implementing targeted strategies, educators can help improve pupils' performance in the Quarterly Examination and overall academic success.

Relationship between Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation and the Academic Difficulties in Science 4

The only factor of self-system thinking based on motivation which showed significant relationship with academic difficulties in Science 4 is self-efficacy. While other motivation factors such as intrinsic motivation, career motivation, self-determination are not significantly correlated. The absence of significant correlation between academic difficulties and other motivation factors indicates that these motivation factors may not be critical in explaining academic struggles. In other words, there may be other factors that have a more significant impact on academic difficulties.

Self-efficacy has a weak and negative correlation with academic difficulties. It is reasonable to infer that pupils with stronger self-efficacy beliefs in learning Science may feel more confident in their ability to understand and master the subject, leading to better academic performance to handle academic difficulties. When the pupils have high self-efficacy, their academic difficulties in learning Science are low. This is because students with high self-efficacy have a strong belief in their ability to complete science tasks successfully, which can increase their motivation, confidence, and perseverance. As a result, they are more likely to engage in learning, persist in the face of challenges, and ultimately achieve better academic outcomes (Honicke & Broadbent, 2016). The interventions aimed at improving pupils' self-efficacy may be effective in reducing academic difficulties in Science 4. This could involve providing pupils with opportunities to experience success in Science through differentiated instruction, offering feedback and encouragement to build their confidence, and helping them develop strategies to overcome challenges and setbacks. By fostering a growth mindset and promoting a sense

of self-efficacy, teachers can help pupils develop the skills and confidence they need to succeed as they overcome their difficulties in learning science.

Relationship between the Pupils' Self-System Thinking Based on Motivation and Their Academic Achievement

The relationship between pupils' self-efficacy, grade motivation, and academic achievement in terms of performance tasks has a weak and positive correlation. This suggests that pupils who have higher self-efficacy and grade motivation tend to perform better in performance tasks. However, the correlation is weak, indicating that there are other variables that have a stronger influence on pupils' performance. Yet, encouraging pupils to believe in their abilities and motivating them with grades may positively impact their academic achievement in Science 4 performance tasks.

Self-efficacy has been found to be a significant predictor of academic achievement, as it can influence pupils' willingness to engage in learning activities and persist in the face of challenges (Zajacova et al., 2005). Similarly, grade motivation can be a powerful incentive for pupils to invest effort and time in their studies. To support pupils' self-efficacy and grade motivation, teachers can provide opportunities for pupils to set goals, receive feedback, and reflect on their progress. Additionally, teachers can create a positive learning environment that values effort and persistence and recognizes pupils' achievements. By doing so, teachers can help pupils develop a growth mindset and a belief in their ability to succeed in Science 4 performance tasks.

On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the academic achievement in terms of written works, quarterly examination, grade weighted average and the self-system thinking based on motivation of the pupils. This suggests that students' self-system thinking based on motivation does not have a significant impact on their academic achievement in these areas. There may be other factors that have a more significant impact on academic achievement in these areas, such as prior knowledge or having a strong foundation of knowledge in a particular subject area, study habits, or teaching methods.

Relationship between Academic Achievement and the Academic Difficulties in Science 4

The academic achievement and academic difficulties in Science 4 show a weak but significant negative correlation in terms of written works. The correlation means that as the academic difficulties increase, the academic achievement in terms of written works decreases, and vice versa. Pupils who encounter more academic difficulties tend to have lower academic achievement in written works, which could potentially indicate a lack of conceptual understanding.

However, the academic difficulties encountered by pupils in Science 4 have no correlation with their academic achievement in these areas: performance tasks, quarterly examination, and grade weighted average. One can consider that these different types of

assessments may measure different aspects of academic achievement than the academic difficulties encountered in Science 4 (Lawrenz et al., 2001). For example, academic difficulties in Science 4 may be more related to conceptual understanding, while performance tasks may assess practical skills, and quarterly examinations may focus on content knowledge.

These findings suggest that written works may be a useful area to target in interventions aimed at reducing academic difficulties. Furthermore, importance of teaching for conceptual understanding and making connections between ideas, rather than just memorizing information. This approach could be particularly relevant for written work in Science 4, as it may help pupils to better understand and apply scientific concepts (Parr & McNaughton, 2014).

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the researchers concluded the following:

1. The self-system thinking of the participants in learning Science 4 subject shows that they are intrinsically, and career-motivated, self-determined, have sense of self-efficacy, and motivated by their grades in science subject. Among these, grade motivation and self-determination are rated the highest, while intrinsic motivation is rated the lowest.
2. The participants did not encounter difficulties in learning Science 4 subject. They find it easy to learn the topics in the first and second quarters of the Science 4.
3. Most participants satisfactorily performed in Science 4 subject, with the highest percentage of academic achievement coming from performance tasks. The participants tend to achieve lower scores or perform less well on quarterly examinations.
4. Self-efficacy is the only motivation factor that shows a significant relationship with academic difficulties in Science 4. Students with stronger self-efficacy beliefs in learning Science may feel more confident in their ability to understand and master the subject, leading to better academic performance and reduced academic difficulties.
5. Self-efficacy and grade motivation have a weak but positive correlation with academic achievement in performance tasks.
6. A weak but significant negative correlation exists between academic achievement and academic difficulties in Science 4 in terms of written works. Pupils who encounter more academic difficulties tend to have lower academic achievement in written works.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested to improve self-system thinking based on motivation, academic achievement, and reduce academic difficulties in Science 4.

1. School Heads can enhance Science teachers' motivation, self-efficacy, and teaching strategies to enhance academic achievement. Regular training workshops on assessment techniques, stress management, and innovative methods can be organized. Lastly, ensure that the curriculum is well aligned with the quarterly examinations. This includes regular reviews and updates to the lesson plans of Science Teachers to reflect on the exam content and structure accurately.
2. Science teachers should improve students' self-efficacy in learning Science through differentiated instruction, feedback, and strategies. Emphasizing good grades and aligning teaching methods with quarterly examination questions and skills is crucial. Regular review sessions and mock exams can help students become familiar with the exam format.
3. Learners should prioritize tasks based on importance and difficulty. Achieving prioritized tasks can boost self-efficacy and keep them motivated. A well-structured study plan can help manage time effectively and ensure that pupils cover all necessary material, enhancing their belief in their ability to succeed. By incorporating self-efficacy and grade motivation into study strategies, pupils can better prepare for quarterly examinations, reduce anxiety, and enhance their academic performance. These strategies help pupils take control of their learning process and build the confidence needed to academic achievement.
4. Parents can help their children improve their performance in quarterly exams by attending parent-teacher meetings, providing necessary study materials, organizing mock exams, and hiring tutors for Science subjects, as well as staying informed about their academic strengths and weaknesses.
5. For future researchers interested in studying the interplay between Grade 4 pupils' self-system and the academic difficulties they encounter in Science education, utilize a combination of theories such as Self-Efficacy Theory and Self-Determination Theory to provide a framework for understanding how grade 4 pupils' self-system thinking influences their academic performance. Moreover, consider contextual factors such as socio-economic status, school environment, and parental involvement to understand how this influences the self-system and academic outcomes. These can contribute valuable knowledge to the field of Science education, helping to enhance the academic experiences and outcomes for Grade 4 pupils.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Investigating the relationship between self-system thinking based on motivation, academic achievement and academic difficulties encountered by pupils in Science 4 raises several important ethical considerations that must be carefully addressed throughout the research process. These considerations aimed to safeguard the rights and well-being of participants, maintain the integrity of research findings, and foster public trust in scientific endeavors.

Ethics clearance from the Research and Development Center of Republic Central Colleges was secured to ensure that the researchers carefully considered the potential risks and benefits of the study and take all reasonable steps to minimize any potential harm to participants which may include addressing physical, psychological, social, and economic risks. The study should not also impose any undue burden or distress on participants.

Obtaining informed consent from participants and their parents or guardians is paramount since they were all minors. This involved providing clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and voluntary participation.

In the process of gathering the data, the parental consents were obtained with the assistance of the advisers per class. Pupils were given assent forms to express willingness to participate in the research. A brief explanation of the objectives and data processing procedures, including anonymity and the importance of voluntary participation were given. The questionnaires were translated from English to Filipino (Tagalog). Both questionnaires were validated by the experts; the RCC Head of the Research and Development Center, the PGES School Head, the PGES Science Coordinator, and the PGES Filipino Coordinator. The translated Science Motivation Questionnaire II (SMQ-II) and Academic Difficulties in Learning Science Questionnaire were used for the Grade 4 pupils to ensure that they fully understand the questions being asked, as they will be able to use their native language to interpret and respond. This can lead to more accurate and reliable data.

Printed survey questionnaires were given to the pupils and those who were absent on the day of implementation were given ample time to answer the questionnaires due to their willingness to participate.

All collected responses from the pupils were encoded by the researchers through an online google form survey since it includes built-in data analysis tools that allows to easily summarize, visualize results, view charts and graphs, as well as export the data to Microsoft excel for further analysis using the SPSS statistical program. Furthermore, the raw grades from 1st and 2nd Quarters of the Grade 4 pupils in the subject Science were given permission by the school head to use as basis and give emphasis to their academic achievement. The researchers implemented appropriate measures to safeguard sensitive information, including personal data and responses. Unique identifiers were assigned to

participants instead of using their names to maintain anonymity. Obtained data were stored securely, and access was restricted to authorized personnel only in accordance with the Data Privacy Act (RA No. 10173).

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